

Universidad de Panamá Publicaciones de Investigaciones y Revistas Científicas 2023 - 2024

Octubre 2024

University of Panama Research Publications & Scientific Journals 2023 - 2024

October 2024

Universidad de Panamá

Puede ver y descargar la información contenida en este documento desde <https://qrco.de/investigaciones>

Autores: Francisco Farnum, Samantha Benítez y Rómulo Escobar

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13983682>

University of Panama

You can view and download the information contained in this document from <https://qrco.de/investigaciones>

Authors: Francisco Farnum, Samantha Benítez y Rómulo Escobar

Autoridades / Authorities

Dr. Eduardo Flores Castro

Rector / Rector

Dr. José Emilio Moreno

Vicerrector Académico / Academic Vice-Rector

Dr. Jaime Javier Gutiérrez

Vicerrector de Investigación y Postgrado / Vice-Rector for
Research and Postgraduate Studies

Mgtr. Arnold Muñoz

Vicerrector Administrativo / Administrative Vice-Rector

Mgtr. Mayanín E. Rodríguez C.

Vicerrectora de Asuntos Estudiantiles / Vice-Rector for
Student Affairs

Mgtr. Ricardo A. Him Chi

Vicerrector de Extensión / Vice-Rector for Extension

Mgtr. Ricardo A. Parker D.

Secretario General / General-Secretary

Mgtr. José Luis Solís Cedeño

Director General de Centros Regionales Universitarios y
Extensiones Universitarias / Director of Regional Centers and
University Extensions

**Vicerrectoría de Investigación y
Postgrado / Vice-Rectorcy for Research
and Postgraduate Studies**

Dr. Jaime Javier Gutiérrez

Vicerrector / Vice-Rector

Dr. Janzel Villalaz

Director de Investigación / Research Director

Dr. Carlos Ramos

Director de Postgrado / Postgraduate Director

Prof. Magdalena Sánchez

Directora Administrativa / Administrative Director

Dr. Francisco Farnum Castro

Coordinador de la Oficina de Publicaciones Académicas y Científicas /
Coordinator of the Academic and Scientific Publications Office

**Dirección General de Planificación y
Evaluación Universitaria / Directorate General
for University Planning and Evaluation**

Mgtr. Adolfo C. Quintero C.

Director General / Managing Director

Dr. Guillermo Gómez

Subdirector de Evaluación / Deputy Director of Evaluation

**Personal responsable del Observatorio Ocupacional /
Staff responsible for the Occupational Observatory**

Dr. Eduardo Valdebenito

Jefe del Observatorio Ocupacional / Head of the Occupational
Observatory

Mgtr. Samantha Benítez de Marquez

Coordinadora / Coordinator

Analista / Analyst

Lic. Rómulo Escobar

Personal de apoyo / Support staff

Lic. Silvia Pringle

Sra. Yaira de Walker

Diseño Gráfico / Graphic Design

Lic. Johana Solís R.

La Universidad de Panamá expande sus vínculos internacionales

Es con gran satisfacción que, como rector de esta prestigiosa casa de estudios, anuncio una nueva etapa en la trayectoria internacional de la Universidad de Panamá. Nuestra institución, siempre comprometida con la excelencia académica y la búsqueda de la verdad, ha dado un paso trascendental al fortalecer sus lazos con universidades y centros de investigación de renombre mundial.

La globalización ha transformado radicalmente el panorama académico, demandando de nuestras instituciones una mayor apertura y colaboración. Conscientes de este nuevo escenario, hemos impulsado una serie de iniciativas destinadas a ampliar nuestra red de contactos y a fomentar la movilidad académica de nuestros estudiantes y profesores. “

En este sentido, hemos suscrito importantes convenios de cooperación con universidades de Europa, Estados Unidos, Asia y América Latina, lo que permitirá a nuestros estudiantes y profesores realizar estancias de investigación en el extranjero, fortaleciendo así sus capacidades de investigación y docencia.

Aspiramos a construir alianzas estratégicas que nos permitan abordar los grandes desafíos que enfrenta la humanidad en la actualidad. Estamos promoviendo la investigación conjunta en áreas como el cambio climático, la salud, la energía renovable y las tecnologías de la información. Creemos firmemente que la colaboración internacional es la clave para encontrar soluciones innovadoras a los problemas más complejos de nuestro tiempo.

La internacionalización de nuestra universidad es una apuesta por el futuro, una inversión en el desarrollo de nuestro país y en el fortalecimiento de nuestra identidad como panameños.

Dr. Eduardo Flores Castro
Rector
Universidad de Panamá

The University of Panama expands its international ties

It is with great satisfaction that, as rector of this prestigious house of studies, I announce a new stage in the international trajectory of the University of Panama. Our institution, always committed to academic excellence and the search for truth, has taken a momentous step by strengthening its ties with world-renowned universities and research centers.

Globalization has radically transformed the academic landscape, demanding greater openness and collaboration from our institutions. Aware of this new scenario, we have promoted a series of initiatives aimed at expanding our network of contacts and promoting the academic mobility of our students and teachers.

In this sense, we have signed important cooperation agreements with universities in Europe, the United States, Asia and Latin America, which will allow our students and professors to carry out research stays abroad, thus strengthening their research and teaching capacities.

We aspire to build strategic alliances that allow us to address the great challenges facing humanity today. We are promoting joint research in areas such as climate change, health, renewable energy and information technologies. We firmly believe that international collaboration is the key to finding innovative solutions to the most complex problems of our time.

The internationalization of our university is a commitment to the future, an investment in the development of our country and in the strengthening of our identity as Panamanians.

Dr. Eduardo Flores Castro
Rector
University of Panama

Impulsando la investigación colaborativa para el desarrollo sostenible

La investigación científica es una piedra angular del desarrollo humano sostenible y ha experimentado cambios transformadores en los últimos años. La creciente complejidad de los desafíos globales requiere más que nunca la colaboración interdisciplinaria y transnacional. En este contexto, la investigación colaborativa y la diplomacia científica se han convertido en herramientas indispensables para desarrollar soluciones efectivas a los problemas apremiantes de la sociedad.

Nuestra universidad está comprometida con el fomento y fortalecimiento de una cultura de colaboración en investigación, innovación y transferencia de tecnología. Al aunar esfuerzos y compartir recursos entre las instituciones académicas, podemos generar conocimientos profundos e impactantes que impulsen la innovación y la transferencia tecnológica. La investigación colaborativa amplía y enriquece la comunidad científica y fortalece las conexiones dentro del ecosistema de investigación, amplificando la influencia de las redes de colaboración académica.

Los beneficios de la investigación colaborativa son enormes. En primer lugar, permite abordar cuestiones complejas que trascien-

den las fronteras disciplinares, aprovechando las diversas perspectivas y conocimientos de los investigadores participantes. En segundo lugar, proporciona acceso a recursos e infraestructuras que pueden ser difíciles de proteger individualmente. Además, contribuye al desarrollo de los jóvenes investigadores ofreciéndoles la oportunidad de participar en proyectos significativos y desarrollar habilidades colaborativas esenciales que son vitales para su crecimiento profesional.

A la comunidad científica —investigadores, instituciones y organizaciones— les extendemos nuestra entusiasta invitación a participar en colaboraciones académicas. Creemos que este es el camino más eficaz hacia la construcción de una sociedad justa y equitativa de ciudadanos globales.

Dr. Jaime Gutiérrez

Vicerrector de Investigación y Postgrado
Universidad de Panamá

Advancing Collaborative Research for Sustainable Development

Scientific research is a cornerstone of sustainable human development, and it has seen transformative changes in recent years. The increasing complexity of global challenges requires interdisciplinary and transnational collaboration more than ever. In this context, collaborative research and science diplomacy have become indispensable tools for developing effective solutions to society's pressing problems.

Our university is committed to fostering and strengthening a culture of collaboration in research, innovation, and technology transfer. By pooling efforts and sharing resources across academic institutions, we can generate profound and impactful knowledge that drives technological innovation and transfer. Collaborative research broadens and enriches the scientific community and fortifies connections within the research ecosystem, amplifying the influence of academic collaboration networks.

The benefits of collaborative research are vast. Firstly, it allows for addressing complex issues that span across disciplinary boundaries, drawing on the diverse

perspectives and expertise of participating researchers. Secondly, it provides access to resources and infrastructure that may be difficult to secure individually. Moreover, it contributes to the development of young researchers by offering them the opportunity to engage in significant projects and develop essential collaborative skills that are vital for their professional growth.

To the scientific community—researchers, institutions, and organizations—we extend our enthusiastic invitation to partake in academic collaborations. We believe this is the most effective path toward building a fair and equitable society of global citizens.

Dr. Jaime Gutiérrez
Vice-Rector for Research and
Postgraduate Studies
University of Panama

Nuestras Publicaciones de Investigaciones 2023 -2024

Selección de artículos de
acceso abierto publicados en
revistas indexadas en Scopus
por área temática

- Ciencias Agropecuarias y Biológicas
- Medicina
- Ciencias Ambientales
- Bioquímica, Genética y Biología Molecular
- Química
- Farmacología, Toxicología y Farmacia
- Ciencias sociales
- Inmunología y Microbiología
- Informática
- Veterinaria
- Ciencias de la Tierra y Planetarias
- Ingeniería
- Física y Astronomía
- Ingeniería Química
- Matemáticas
- Enfermería
- Profesiones de la Salud
- Energía
- Ciencia de Materiales
- Ciencias de Decisión
- Artes y Humanidades
- Negocios, Gestión y Contabilidad
- Odontología
- Multidisciplinar

Our Research Publications 2023 -2024

Selection of Open Access
articles published in journals
indexed in Scopus by
thematic area

- Agricultural and Biological Sciences
- Medicine
- Environmental Science
- Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology
- Chemistry
- Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics
- Social Sciences
- Immunology and Microbiology
- Computer Science
- Veterinary
- Earth and Planetary Sciences
- Engineering
- Physics and Astronomy
- Chemical Engineering
- Mathematics
- Nursing
- Health Professions
- Energy
- Materials Science
- Decision Sciences
- Arts and Humanities
- Business, Management and Accounting
- Dentistry
- Multidisciplinary

Ciencias Agropecuarias y Biológicas / Agricultural and Biological Sciences

Article • *Open access* /

1	Non-volatile leaves compounds LC-MS profile of the two Cuban Piper aduncum L. subspecies Perfil de CL-SM de compuestos no volátiles de las hojas de las dos subspecies cubanas de Piper aduncum L.	2024
2	Tree demographic strategies largely overlap across succession in Neotropical wet and dry forest communities	2024
3	A Test of Immune Priming in the Kissing Bug <i>Rhodnius pallescens</i> (Hemiptera: Reduviidae) against the Entomopathogenic Fungus <i>Beauveria bassiana</i> (Hypocreales: Cordycipitaceae) in Panama	2024
4	Multiple Infections, Nutrient Deficiencies, and Inflammation as Determinants of Anemia and Iron Status during Pregnancy: The MINDI Cohort	2024
5	Hot Iron Branding of Beef Cattle: Process Characterization, Implications for Animal Welfare, and Its Efficiency for Cattle Individual Identification	2024
6	Changes in the Carotenoids of <i>Zamia dressleri</i> Leaves during Development	2024
7	Doxycycline is a viable alternative to tetracycline for use in insect Tet-Off transgenic sexing systems, as assessed in the blowflies <i>Cochliomyia hominivorax</i> and <i>Lucilia cuprina</i> (Diptera: Calliphoridae)	2024
8	Illuminating arthropod diversity in a tropical forest: Assessing biodiversity by automatic light trapping and DNA metabarcoding	2024
9	The plasticity of immune memory in invertebrates	2024
10	Taxonomic notes on <i>Pertyella</i> Mickel, 1952 (Hymenoptera; Mutillidae): Morphological characters rediscussion, new species, new combinations, new records, and species grouping Notas taxonómicas sobre <i>Pertyella</i> Mickel, 1952 (Hymenoptera: Mutillidae): rediscusión de caracteres morfológicos, especie nueva, combinaciones nuevas, registros nuevos y agrupaciones de especies	2024
11	A new species of <i>Bernardia</i> (Euphorbiaceae, Acalyphoideae) with stellate trichomes from South America	2024
12	<i>Kevinilla</i> , a new velvet ant genus in the Sphaerophthalminae (Hymenoptera: Mutillidae)	2024
13	The Trichoptera of Panama. XXV. Eight new country records of caddisflies (Insecta, Trichoptera)	2024
14	Estimating the body size of orchid bees (Hymenoptera: Apidae: Euglossini) using the distance between their tegulae	2024

15	Exploring the Biomedical Potential of Endophytic Fungi Isolated from Panamanian Mangroves	2024
16	A new species of Cocinachernes (Pseudoscorpiones: Chernetidae) associated with mosses in Mexico	2024
17	Wood trait preferences of Neotropical xylophagous beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)	2024
18	Fungal community dissimilarity predicts plant–soil feedback strength in a lowland tropical forest	2024
19	Factors associated with the consumption of fruits and vegetables in latin american university students Factores asociados al consumo de frutas y verduras en estudiantes universitarios de latinoamerica	2023
20	Records of Predation of Reptiles and Amphibians by Arthropods in the Gatun Lake Recreational Area, Colón, Panamá Registros de Depredación de Reptiles y Anfibios por Artrópodos en el Área Recreativa Lago Gatún, Colón, Panamá	2023
21	Assessment of the Quality, Chemometric and Pollen Diversity of Apis mellifera Honey from Different Seasonal Harvests	2023
22	Recovery and Characterization of Spermatozoa in a Neotropical, Terrestrial, Direct-Developing Riparian Frog (<i>Craugastor evanescens</i>) through Hormonal Stimulation	2023
23	Tropical butterflies use thermal buffering and thermal tolerance as alternative strategies to cope with temperature increase	2023
24	Species richness and abundance of bats (Order: Chiroptera) in the Mamóní Valley Preserve, Republic of Panama Riqueza y abundancia de especies de murciélagos (Orden: Chiroptera) de la Reserva del Valle Mamóní, República de Panamá	2023
25	Predation of the fiddler crab, <i>Minuca osa</i> (Brachyura: Ocypodidae), by <i>Eudocimus albus</i> (Pelecaniformes: Threskiornithidae) from Ponuga, Veraguas, Panama Depredación del cangrejo violinista, <i>Minuca osa</i> (Brachyura: Ocypodidae), por <i>Eudocimus albus</i> (Pelecaniformes: Threskiornithidae) en Ponuga, Veraguas, Panamá	2023
26	Foraging patterns of bees in watermelon (<i>Citrullus lanatus</i> Thunb.) flowers in Panama	2023
27	Building a Teleost Fish Traceability Program Based on Genetic Data from Pacific Panama Fish Markets	2023
28	Abundance, occurrence and time series: long-term monitoring of social insects in a tropical rainforest	2023
29	Catalog and distribution atlas of the Scarabaeoidea (Insecta: Coleoptera) of El Salvador Catálogo y atlas de distribución de los Scarabaeoidea (Insecta: Coleoptera) de El Salvador	2023

30	Diversity and Abundance of Amphibians In The London 50 HA Environmental Compensation Project, Panama Diversity and Abundance of Amphibians in the London 50 HA Environmental Compensation Project, Panama	2023
31	First report of the invasive ant <i>Nylanderia fulva</i> (Mayr, 1862) (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) in Panama	2023
32	Ovulatory response of Beef and Dairy cows subjected to two follicular emergence synchronization protocols before superovulation	2023
33	Size and weight of <i>Cardisoma crassum</i> and <i>Ucides occidentalis</i> collected by artisanal fishing in Chame, Panamanian Pacific Talla y peso de <i>Cardisoma crassum</i> y <i>Ucides occidentalis</i> colectados por la pesca artesanal en Chame, Pacífico panameño	2023
34	Assessment of nursery areas for the scalloped hammerhead shark (<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>) across the Eastern Tropical Pacific using a stable isotopes approach	2023
35	Species swarms and their caterpillar colonisers: phylogeny and polyphenols determine host plant specificity in New Guinean Lepidoptera	2023
36	A new species of <i>Casearia</i> Jacq. (Salicaceae) from Central Panama and insights into its phylogenetic position within the genus	2023
37	First predation report of <i>Gecarcinus quadratus</i> (Brachyura: Gecarcinidae) by <i>Ancylometes bogotensis</i> (Arachnida: Ctenidae) in Coiba Island, Panama	2023
38	Malnutrition and unhealthy eating habits in Panamanian firefighters Malnutrición e inadecuados hábitos de alimentación en bomberos de Panamá	2023
39	Three new species and a new record of <i>Monstera</i> Adans. sect. <i>Marcgraviopsis</i> Madison (Araceae: Monsteroideae: Monstereae) from the Caribbean watershed in Costa Rica and Panama	2023
40	Effects of paraformic acid supplementation, as an antibiotic replacement, on growth performance, intestinal morphology and gut microbiota of nursery pigs.	2023
41	Molecular detection of <i>Ehrlichia canis</i> and <i>Ehrlichia ewingii</i> coinfection in a dog in Ecuador Detección molecular de coinfección por <i>Ehrlichia canis</i> y <i>Ehrlichia ewingii</i> en un perro en Ecuador	2023
42	<i>Selaginella</i> P.Beauv. (Selaginellaceae) in the state of Maranhão, northeastern, Brazil: A floristic survey and a new record for the Cerrado domain <i>Selaginella</i> P.Beauv. (Selaginellaceae) no estado do Maranhão, nordeste, Brasil: Levantamento florístico e novo registro para o domínio Cerrado	2023
43	Hematological, biochemical, and growth parameters of Sprague Dawley rat of the Scientific Research and High Technology Services Institute of Panama Parámetros hematológicos, bioquímicos y de crecimiento en ratas del Bioterio del Instituto de Investigaciones Científicas y Servicios de Alta Tecnología de Panamá	2023

44	Segregation by size in the mouthless crab <i>Cardisoma crassum</i> (Brachyura: Gecarcinidae) from Ponuga, Veraguas, Panama Segregación por talla en el cangrejo sin boca, <i>Cardisoma crassum</i> (Brachyura: Gecarcinidae) en Ponuga, Veraguas, Panamá	2023
45	Distributions, range extensions and host list update for four phoretic mite genera (Acari: Klinckowstroemiidae) on Passalidae (Coleoptera)	2023
46	Two new records of the fern genus <i>Lindsaea dryand.</i> Ex Sm. (Lindsaeaceae) from Panama	2023
47	STATIS multivariate three-way method for evaluating quality of life after corneal surgery: Methodology and case study in Costa Rica	2023
48	Food web structure and microenvironment affect Chagas disease vector infection and abundance in a rural landscape	2023
49	Towards a functional classification of poorly known tropical insects: The case of rhinoceros beetles (Coleoptera, Dynastinae) in Panama	2023
50	A new species of <i>Epichernes</i> (Pseudoscorpiones: Chernetidae) associated with rodents in Costa Rica	2023
51	Towards effective reforestation: growth and commercial value of four commonly planted tropical timber species on infertile soils in Panama	2023

Medicine / Medicina

Article • *Open access*

1	Risk factors associated with amputations in patients with diabetic foot infection. Seven years of experience in a reference hospital in Panama. The diabetic foot study group at Chiriqui (the FOOTCHI study group)	2024
2	Non-volatile leaves compounds LC-MS profile of the two Cuban Piper aduncum L. subspecies Perfil de CL-SM de compuestos no volátiles de las hojas de las dos subspecies cubanas de Piper aduncum L.	2024
3	Epidemiology and Genetic Characterization of Leishmania RNA Virus in Leishmania (Viannia) spp. Isolates from Cutaneous Leishmaniasis Endemic Areas in Panama	2024
4	Global burden and strength of evidence for 88 risk factors in 204 countries and 811 subnational locations, 1990–2021: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021	2024
5	Global burden of 288 causes of death and life expectancy decomposition in 204 countries and territories and 811 subnational locations, 1990–2021: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021	2024
6	Spatiotemporal Analysis of Malaria Transmission in the Autonomous Indigenous Regions of Panama, Central America, 2015–2022	2024
7	Evidence in the diagnosis and treatment of postpartum depression: a narrative review Evidencias en el diagnóstico y tratamiento de la depresión posparto: revisión narrativa	2024
8	Experiences in the use of multiple doses of convalescent plasma in critically ill patients with COVID-19: An early phase 1 descriptive study	2024
9	MSG-15: Super-Bioavailability Itraconazole Versus Conventional Itraconazole in the Treatment of Endemic Mycoses - A Multicenter, Open-Label, Randomized Comparative Trial	2024
10	Norovirus in children under 2 years of age: an epidemiological study in Panama during the COVID-19 pandemic	2024
11	Placental concentrations of xenoestrogenic organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls and assessment of their xenoestrogenicity in the PA-MAMI mother-child cohort	2024
12	Understanding the conservation-genetics gap in Latin America: challenges and opportunities to integrate genetics into conservation practices	2024
13	Prevalence of syphilis among people living with HIV who attend a large urban antiretroviral therapy clinic in Panama: a cross-sectional epidemiological study	2024

14	Study of Text Patterns Found on Social Networks of Mental Health Reactions to COVID-19	2024
15	Snakebite-Associated Infections: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis	2024
16	Central American and Caribbean Consensus Document for the Optimal Management of Oral Anticoagulation in Patients with Non-Valvular Atrial Fibrillation Endorsed by the Central American and Caribbean Society of Arterial Hypertension and Cardiovascular Prevention	2024
17	Exploring the Biomedical Potential of Endophytic Fungi Isolated from Panamanian Mangroves	2024
18	Real-time RT-PCR for Venezuelan equine encephalitis complex, Madariaga, and Eastern equine encephalitis viruses: application in human and mosquito public health surveillance in Panama	2023
19	Detection of parechovirus A in respiratory, gastrointestinal, and neurological clinical samples of pediatric patients from Panama (2014–2015)	2023
20	Synergistic Combination of NAPROC-13 and NMR 13C DFT Calculations: A Powerful Approach for Revising the Structure of Natural Products	2023
21	HIV-1 Low-Frequency Variants Identified in Antiretroviral-Naïve Subjects with Virologic Failure after 12 Months of Follow-Up in Panama	2023
22	Identification of Secondary Metabolites from the Mangrove-Endophyte <i>Lasiodiplodia iranensis</i> F0619 by UPLC-ESI-MS/MS	2023
23	Acute fetal cardiovascular adaptation to artificial placenta in sheep model	2023
24	Impact of a Nurse-Led Multidisciplinary Heart Failure Clinic in a Low-Resource Setting: Experience in a Latin American Public Healthcare System	2023
25	An interesting case of survival to multiple ruptures of aneurysms, with persistent trigeminal artery, cranial nerve deficit, and evolutionary exposure of neurovascular treatment	2023
26	Halo sign in fetal cytomegalovirus infection: cerebral imaging abnormalities and postmortem histopathology in 35 infected fetuses	2023
27	Detection of Leishmania RNA Virus 1 in <i>Leishmania (Viannia) panamensis</i> Isolates, Panama	2023
28	Insights into the Genetic Diversity of <i>Leishmania (Viannia) panamensis</i> in Panama, Inferred via Multilocus Sequence Typing (MLST)	2023
29	Brain cortical maturation assessed by magnetic resonance imaging in unaffected or mildly affected fetuses with cytomegalovirus infection	2023
30	Physical Inactivity and Sedentary Behaviour among Panamanian Adults: Results from the National Health Survey of Panama (ENSPA) 2019	2023
31	An Artificial Placenta Experimental System in Sheep: Critical Issues for Successful Transition and Survival up to One Week	2023
32	Prevalence of Anemia and Iron Deficiency in Women of Reproductive Age in Cuba and Associated Factors	2023

33	Prevalence of Plasmid-Associated Tetracycline Resistance Genes in Multidrug-Resistant Escherichia coli Strains Isolated from Environmental, Animal and Human Samples in Panama	2023
34	Associations Between Polygenic Risk Score Loading, Psychosis Liability, and Clozapine Use Among Individuals With Schizophrenia	2023
35	A new host-targeted antiviral cyclolignan (SAU-22.107) for Dengue Virus infection in cell cultures. Potential action mechanisms based on cell imaging	2023
36	Differential susceptibility of human microglia HMC3 cells and brain microvascular endothelial HBEC-5i cells to Mayaro and Una virus infection	2023
37	Barriers and Opportunities for Clinical Nutritionists in 13 Latin American Countries: A Qualitative Study	2023
38	Tropical splenomegaly in a migrant-in-transit crossing the Darien gap, Panamá: A probable case of hyper-reactive malarial splenomegaly	2023
39	From production to impacts on health and the environment: an analysis of food systems in Brazil, Colombia and Panama Da produção aos impactos na saúde e no ambiente: uma análise dos sistemas alimentares de Brasil, Colômbia e Panamá	2023
40	Genetic Diversity and New Sequence Types of Escherichia coli Coharboring β -Lactamases and PMQR Genes Isolated from Domestic Dogs in Central Panama	2023
41	Dating violence prevalence and risk factors among adolescents (14–19 years) in urban public schools in Panama	2023

Ciencias Ambientales / Environmental Science

Article • *Open access*

1	Changes in the Carotenoids of <i>Zamia dressleri</i> Leaves during Development	2024
2	Doxycycline is a viable alternative to tetracycline for use in insect Tet-Off transgenic sexing systems, as assessed in the blowflies <i>Cochliomyia hominivorax</i> and <i>Lucilia cuprina</i> (Diptera: Calliphoridae)	2024
3	Illuminating arthropod diversity in a tropical forest: Assessing biodiversity by automatic light trapping and DNA metabarcoding	2024
4	Placental concentrations of xenoestrogenic organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls and assessment of their xenoestrogenicity in the PA-MAMI mother-child cohort	2024
5	A new genus of Anacardiaceae based on wood from the Tepetate Formation (upper Eocene) of Baja California Sur, Mexico	2024
6	The Trichoptera of Panama. XXV. Eight new country records of caddisflies (Insecta, Trichoptera)	2024
7	Contribution of Argentinian B Corporations to Sustainable Development Goals: Empirical Analysis Based on Their Practices and Solutions to Socioenvironmental Problems	2024
8	Elucidating Best Geospatial Estimation Method Applied to Environmental Sciences	2024
9	Ongoing harlequin toad declines suggest the amphibian extinction crisis is still an emergency	2023
10	Body Temperature Drop as a Humane Endpoint in Snake Venom-Lethality Neutralization Tests	2023
11	Spatial Analysis of Territorial Connectivity and Accessibility in the Province of Coclé in Panama	2023
12	Thermoregulatory ability and mechanism do not differ consistently between neotropical and temperate butterflies	2023
13	Predation of the fiddler crab, <i>Minuca osa</i> (Brachyura: Ocypodidae), by <i>Eudocimus albus</i> (Pelecaniformes: Threskiornithidae) from Ponuga, Veraguas, Panama Depredación del cangrejo violinista, <i>Minuca osa</i> (Brachyura: Ocypodidae), por <i>Eudocimus albus</i> (Pelecaniformes: Threskiornithidae) en Ponuga, Veraguas, Panamá	2023
14	Foraging patterns of bees in watermelon (<i>Citrullus lanatus</i> Thunb.) flowers in Panama	2023
15	Abundance, occurrence and time series: long-term monitoring of social insects in a tropical rainforest	2023

16	Physical Inactivity and Sedentary Behaviour among Panamanian Adults: Results from the National Health Survey of Panama (ENSPA) 2019	2023
17	First report of the invasive ant <i>Nylanderia fulva</i> (Mayr, 1862) (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) in Panama	2023
18	Prevalence of Anemia and Iron Deficiency in Women of Reproductive Age in Cuba and Associated Factors	2023
19	Assessment of nursery areas for the scalloped hammerhead shark (<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>) across the Eastern Tropical Pacific using a stable isotopes approach	2023
20	Species swarms and their caterpillar colonisers: phylogeny and polyphenols determine host plant specificity in New Guinean Lepidoptera	2023
21	Three new species and a new record of <i>Monstera</i> Adans. sect. <i>Marcgraviopsis</i> Madison (Araceae: Monsteroideae: Monstereae) from the Caribbean watershed in Costa Rica and Panama	2023
22	Effects of paraformic acid supplementation, as an antibiotic replacement, on growth performance, intestinal morphology and gut microbiota of nursery pigs.	2023
23	Segregation by size in the mouthless crab <i>Cardisoma crassum</i> (Brachyura: Gecarcinidae) from Ponuga, Veraguas, Panama Segregación por talla en el cangrejo sin boca, <i>Cardisoma crassum</i> (Brachyura: Gecarcinidae) en Ponuga, Veraguas, Panamá	2023
24	Two new records of the fern genus <i>Lindsaea</i> Dryand. Ex Sm. (Lindsaeaceae) from Panama	2023
25	The emergency medical services of Madrid tested: analysis of the spatial-temporal performance of SAMUR-PC in the first months of the postCOVID-19 new normality period El sistema médico de emergencias de Madrid a prueba: análisis del rendimiento espaciotemporal del SAMUR-PC en los primeros meses de la nueva normalidad postCOVID-19	2023
26	Food web structure and microenvironment affect Chagas disease vector infection and abundance in a rural landscape	2023

Bioquímica, Genética y Biología Molecular/ Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology

Article • *Open access*

1	Risk factors associated with amputations in patients with diabetic foot infection. Seven years of experience in a reference hospital in Panama. The diabetic foot study group at Chiriqui (the FOOTCHI study group)	2024
2	Isolation of Alpha-Glucosidase Inhibitors from the Panamanian Mangrove Plant <i>Mora oleifera</i> (Triana ex Hemsl.) Ducke	2024
3	Molecular Diversity from Longipinenes of <i>Santolina viscosa</i> Lag. through Acid Catalysis: Biocidal Activity	2024
4	Potent, selective and reversible hMAO-B inhibition by benzalphthalides: Synthesis, enzymatic and cellular evaluations and virtual docking and predictive studies	2024
5	BZ-97: A Promising Compound Against <i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i>	2024
6	Illuminating arthropod diversity in a tropical forest: Assessing biodiversity by automatic light trapping and DNA metabarcoding	2024
7	The plasticity of immune memory in invertebrates	2024
8	Dispersion patterns of SARS-CoV-2 variants Gamma, Lambda and Mu in Latin America and the Caribbean	2024
9	Placental concentrations of xenoestrogenic organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls and assessment of their xenoestrogenicity in the PA-MAMI mother-child cohort	2024
10	Understanding the conservation-genetics gap in Latin America: challenges and opportunities to integrate genetics into conservation practices	2024
11	Anti-Trypanosomal Bufadienolides from the Oocytes of the Toad <i>Rhinella alata</i> (Anura, Bufonidae)	2024
12	Mixed success for carbon payments and subsidies in support of forest restoration in the neotropics	2023
13	Direct determination of high-order transverse ligand field parameters via μ SQUID-EPR in a $\text{Et}_4\text{N}[\text{160GdPc}_2]$ SMM	2023
14	Synergistic Combination of NAPROC-13 and NMR ^{13}C DFT Calculations: A Powerful Approach for Revising the Structure of Natural Products	2023
15	Navigating the Chemical Space and Chemical Multiverse of a Unified Latin American Natural Product Database: LANaPDB	2023
16	Identification of Secondary Metabolites from the Mangrove-Endophyte <i>Lasiodiplodia iranensis</i> F0619 by UPLC-ESI-MS/MS	2023

17	Insights into the Genetic Diversity of <i>Leishmania (Viannia) panamensis</i> in Panama, Inferred via Multilocus Sequence Typing (MLST)	2023
18	An Artificial Placenta Experimental System in Sheep: Critical Issues for Successful Transition and Survival up to One Week	2023
19	Polyphenols with Anti-Inflammatory Properties: Synthesis and Biological Activity of Novel Curcumin Derivatives	2023
20	Prevalence of Plasmid-Associated Tetracycline Resistance Genes in Multidrug-Resistant <i>Escherichia coli</i> Strains Isolated from Environmental, Animal and Human Samples in Panama	2023
21	Molecular-Engineered Biradicals Based on the YIII-Phthalocyanine Platform	2023
22	A new host-targeted antiviral cyclolignan (SAU-22.107) for Dengue Virus infection in cell cultures. Potential action mechanisms based on cell imaging	2023
23	Effects of paraformic acid supplementation, as an antibiotic replacement, on growth performance, intestinal morphology and gut microbiota of nursery pigs.	2023
24	Genetic Diversity and New Sequence Types of <i>Escherichia coli</i> Coharboring β -Lactamases and PMQR Genes Isolated from Domestic Dogs in Central Panama	2023

Química / Chemistry

Article • *Open access*

1	Potent, selective and reversible hMAO-B inhibition by benzalphthalides: Synthesis, enzymatic and cellular evaluations and virtual docking and predictive studies	2024
2	Unique Double and Triple Decker Arrangements of Rare-Earth 9,10-Diborataanthracene Complexes Featuring Single-Molecule Magnet Characteristics	2024
3	Dispersion patterns of SARS-CoV-2 variants Gamma, Lambda and Mu in Latin America and the Caribbean	2024
4	A chemically functionalized glass support for gold and silver metallic nanoparticle analysis with LIBS	2024
5	Anti-Trypanosomal Bufadienolides from the Oocytes of the Toad <i>Rhinella alata</i> (Anura, Bufonidae)	2024
6	Insight into ferromagnetic interactions in CuII-LnIII dimers with a compartmental ligand	2023
7	Mixed success for carbon payments and subsidies in support of forest restoration in the neotropics	2023
8	FTIR-ATR detection method for emerging C3-plants-derived adulterants in honey: Beet, dates, and carob syrups	2023
9	Direct determination of high-order transverse ligand field parameters via μ SQUID-EPR in a Et ₄ N[160GdPc ₂] SMM	2023
10	Synergistic Combination of NAPROC-13 and NMR 13C DFT Calculations: A Powerful Approach for Revising the Structure of Natural Products	2023
11	Comparison of Shear Bond Strength and Microleakage between Activa™ Bioactive Restorative™ and Bulk-Fill Composites—An In Vitro Study	2023
12	Thermalization of Nuclear Spins in Lanthanide Molecular Magnets	2023
13	Molecular Lanthanide Switches for Magnetism and Photoluminescence	2023
14	Polyphenols with Anti-Inflammatory Properties: Synthesis and Biological Activity of Novel Curcumin Derivatives	2023
15	Molecular-Engineered Biradicals Based on the YIII-Phthalocyanine Platform	2023
16	Binuclear Lanthanide Complexes Based on 4-Picoline-N-oxide: From Sensitized Luminescence to Single-Molecule Magnet Characteristics	2023
17	Rapid, reliable and easy-to-perform chemometric-less method for rice syrup adulterated honey detection using FTIR-ATR	2023

Farmacología, Toxicología y Farmacia / Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics

Article • *Open access*

1	Non-volatile leaves compounds LC-MS profile of the two Cuban Piper aduncum L. subspecies Perfil de CL-SM de compuestos no volátiles de las hojas de las dos subspecies cubanas de Piper aduncum L.	2024
2	Isolation of Alpha-Glucosidase Inhibitors from the Panamanian Mangrove Plant Mora oleifera (Triana ex Hemsl.) Ducke	2024
3	Potent, selective and reversible hMAO-B inhibition by benzalphthalides: Synthesis, enzymatic and cellular evaluations and virtual docking and predictive studies	2024
4	BZ-97: A Promising Compound Against Trypanosoma cruzi	2024
5	Antiproliferative Activity of Extracts Containing Flavonoids from In Vitro Callus Cultures of Astragalus onobrychis	2024
6	Exploring the Biomedical Potential of Endophytic Fungi Isolated from Panamanian Mangroves	2024
7	Anti-Trypanosomal Bufadienolides from the Oocytes of the Toad Rhinella alata (Anura, Bufonidae)	2024
8	Elucidating Best Geospatial Estimation Method Applied to Environmental Sciences	2024
9	Synergistic Combination of NAPROC-13 and NMR 13C DFT Calculations: A Powerful Approach for Revising the Structure of Natural Products	2023
10	Navigating the Chemical Space and Chemical Multiverse of a Unified Latin American Natural Product Database: LANaPDB	2023
11	Body Temperature Drop as a Humane Endpoint in Snake Venom-Lethality Neutralization Tests	2023
12	Aryltetralin lignans from Hyptis brachiata inhibiting T lymphocyte proliferation	2023
13	Prevalence of Plasmid-Associated Tetracycline Resistance Genes in Multidrug-Resistant Escherichia coli Strains Isolated from Environmental, Animal and Human Samples in Panama	2023

Ciencias Sociales / Social Sciences

Article • *Open access*

1	Damped Oscillations—A Smartphone Approach	2024
2	The needed link between open science and science diplomacy—A Latin American perspective	2024
3	Social perception of the connectivity and quality of sidewalks in the Metropolitan Area of Panama	2024
4	Contribution of Argentinian B Corporations to Sustainable Development Goals: Empirical Analysis Based on Their Practices and Solutions to Socioenvironmental Problems	2024
5	Assessment of the Quality, Chemometric and Pollen Diversity of <i>Apis mellifera</i> Honey from Different Seasonal Harvests	2023
6	Spatial Analysis of Territorial Connectivity and Accessibility in the Province of Coclé in Panama	2023
7	Cultural Imaginaries and Complex Thinking: Impact of Cultural Education on the Development of Perceived Achievement of Complex Thinking in Undergraduates	2023
8	The broken bridge and the problems of crossing troubled waters: critical pedagogies in the digital age El puente roto y los problemas para atravesar aguas turbulentas: las pedagogías críticas en la era digital	2023
9	Temporal Changes in the Prevalence of External Auditory Exostoses in Pre-Columbian Panama Cambios temporales en la prevalencia de la exostosis del oído externo en Panamá precolombino	2023
10	Network analysis of collaborative relationships of WEEE companies in Panama Análisis reticular de las relaciones de colaboración de las empresas de desechos tecnológicos de Panamá	2023
11	Reflections on the educational practice of active Panamanian mathematics teachers*	2023
12	The emergency medical services of Madrid tested: analysis of the spatial-temporal performance of SAMUR-PC in the first months of the postCOVID-19 new normality period El sistema médico de emergencias de Madrid a prueba: análisis del rendimiento espaciotemporal del SAMUR-PC en los primeros meses de la nueva normalidad postCOVID-19	2023
13	Knowledge, Perceptions, and Practices on Risks and Disasters Among Medical Students. A Multicenter Cross-Sectional Study in 9 Latin American and Caribbean Countries	2023

Inmunología y Microbiología / Immunology and Microbiology

Article • *Open access*

1	Epidemiology and Genetic Characterization of Leishmania RNA Virus in Leishmania (Viannia) spp. Isolates from Cutaneous Leishmaniasis Endemic Areas in Panama	2024
2	Spatiotemporal Analysis of Malaria Transmission in the Autonomous Indigenous Regions of Panama, Central America, 2015–2022	2024
3	Snakebite-Associated Infections: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis	2024
4	Detection of parechovirus A in respiratory, gastrointestinal, and neurological clinical samples of pediatric patients from Panama (2014–2015)	2023
5	Assessment of the Quality, Chemometric and Pollen Diversity of Apis mellifera Honey from Different Seasonal Harvests	2023
6	Insights into the Genetic Diversity of Leishmania (Viannia) panamensis in Panama, Inferred via Multilocus Sequence Typing (MLST)	2023
7	Prevalence of Plasmid-Associated Tetracycline Resistance Genes in Multidrug-Resistant Escherichia coli Strains Isolated from Environmental, Animal and Human Samples in Panama	2023
8	A new host-targeted antiviral cyclolignan (SAU-22.107) for Dengue Virus infection in cell cultures. Potential action mechanisms based on cell imaging	2023
9	Differential susceptibility of human microglia HMC3 cells and brain microvascular endothelial HBEC-5i cells to Mayaro and Una virus infection	2023
10	Molecular detection of Ehrlichia canis and Ehrlichia ewingii coinfection in a dog in Ecuador Detección molecular de coinfección por Ehrlichia canis y Ehrlichia ewingii en un perro en Ecuador	2023

Informática / Computer Science

Article • *Open access*

1	Contribution of Argentinian B Corporations to Sustainable Development Goals: Empirical Analysis Based on Their Practices and Solutions to Socioenvironmental Problems	2024
2	Trends and challenges in chemoinformatics research in Latin America	2023
3	Deep metric learning for the classification of MALDI-TOF spectral signatures from multiple species of neotropical disease vectors	2023
4	Spatial Analysis of Territorial Connectivity and Accessibility in the Province of Coclé in Panama	2023
5	X-STATIS: A Multivariate Approach to Characterize the Evolution of E-Participation, from a Global Perspective	2023
6	Floating Interleaved Boost Converter with Zero-Ripple Input Current Using Variable Inductor	2023
7	Polyphenols with Anti-Inflammatory Properties: Synthesis and Biological Activity of Novel Curcumin Derivatives	2023
8	Towards Fully Secure 5G Ultra-Low Latency Communications: A Cost-Security Functions Analysis	2023
9	Assessing Panamanian hospitals' performance with alternative frontier methods	2023

Veterinaria / Veterinary

Article • *Open access*

1	Genomic insights of <i>S. aureus</i> associated with bovine mastitis in a high livestock activity region of Mexico	2024
2	Hot Iron Branding of Beef Cattle: Process Characterization, Implications for Animal Welfare, and Its Efficiency for Cattle Individual Identification	2024
3	Recovery and Characterization of Spermatozoa in a Neotropical, Terrestrial, Direct-Developing Riparian Frog (<i>Craugastor evanesco</i>) through Hormonal Stimulation	2023
4	Building a Teleost Fish Traceability Program Based on Genetic Data from Pacific Panama Fish Markets	2023
5	Ovulatory response of Beef and Dairy cows subjected to two follicular emergence synchronization protocols before superovulation	2023
6	Effects of paraformic acid supplementation, as an antibiotic replacement, on growth performance, intestinal morphology and gut microbiota of nursery pigs	2023
7	Molecular detection of <i>Ehrlichia canis</i> and <i>Ehrlichia ewingii</i> coinfection in a dog in Ecuador Detección molecular de coinfección por <i>Ehrlichia canis</i> y <i>Ehrlichia ewingii</i> en un perro en Ecuador	2023
8	Hematological, biochemical, and growth parameters of Sprague Dawley rat of the Scientific Research and High Technology Services Institute of Panama Parámetros hematológicos, bioquímicos y de crecimiento en ratas del Bioterio del Instituto de Investigaciones Científicas y Servicios de Alta Tecnología de Panamá	2023

Ciencias de la Tierra y Planetarias / Earth and Planetary Sciences

Article • *Open access*

1	Social perception of the connectivity and quality of sidewalks in the Metropolitan Area of Panama	2024
2	A new genus of Anacardiaceae based on wood from the Tepetate Formation (upper Eocene) of Baja California Sur, Mexico	2024
3	Past and Present Drivers of Karst Formation of Ciénega de El Mangle, Panama	2023
4	Ongoing harlequin toad declines suggest the amphibian extinction crisis is still an emergency	2023
5	Foraging patterns of bees in watermelon (<i>Citrullus lanatus</i> Thunb.) flowers in Panama	2023
6	Assessment of nursery areas for the scalloped hammerhead shark (<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>) across the Eastern Tropical Pacific using a stable isotopes approach	2023
7	The emergency medical services of Madrid tested: analysis of the spatial-temporal performance of SAMUR-PC in the first months of the postCOVID-19 new normality period El sistema médico de emergencias de Madrid a prueba: análisis del rendimiento espaciotemporal del SAMUR-PC en los primeros meses de la nueva normalidad postCOVID-19	2023

Ingeniería / Engineering

Article • *Open access*

1	A Finite-Set Integral Sliding Modes Predictive Control for a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor Drive System	2024
2	Mechanical Characterization of the Erythrocyte Membrane Using a Capacitor-Based Technique	2024
3	A High-Voltage-Gain DC–DC Boost Converter with Zero-Ripple Input Current for Renewable Applications	2023
4	X-STATIS: A Multivariate Approach to Characterize the Evolution of E-Participation, from a Global Perspective	2023
5	Assessment of nursery areas for the scalloped hammerhead shark (<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>) across the Eastern Tropical Pacific using a stable isotopes approach	2023

Física y Astronomía / Physics and Astronomy

Article • *Open access*

1	Dispersion patterns of SARS-CoV-2 variants Gamma, Lambda and Mu in Latin America and the Caribbean	2024
2	Damped Oscillations—A Smartphone Approach	2024
3	Mixed success for carbon payments and subsidies in support of forest restoration in the neotropics	2023
4	Direct determination of high-order transverse ligand field parameters via μ SQUID-EPR in a Et ₄ N[160GdPc ₂] SMM	2023
5	Binuclear Lanthanide Complexes Based on 4-Picoline-N-oxide: From Sensitized Luminescence to Single-Molecule Magnet Characteristics	2023

Ingeniería Química / Chemical Engineering

Article • *Open access*

1	Unique Double and Triple Decker Arrangements of Rare-Earth 9,10-Diborataanthracene Complexes Featuring Single-Molecule Magnet Characteristics	2024
2	Molecular Lanthanide Switches for Magnetism and Photoluminescence	2023
3	Polyphenols with Anti-Inflammatory Properties: Synthesis and Biological Activity of Novel Curcumin Derivatives	2023
4	Molecular-Engineered Biradicals Based on the YIII-Phthalocyanine Platform	2023

Matemáticas / Mathematics

Article • *Open access*

1	A High-Voltage-Gain DC–DC Boost Converter with Zero-Ripple Input Current for Renewable Applications	2023
2	X-STATIS: A Multivariate Approach to Characterize the Evolution of E-Participation, from a Global Perspective	2023
3	STATIS multivariate three-way method for evaluating quality of life after corneal surgery: Methodology and case study in Costa Rica	2023
4	The Argument and Demonstration Exemplified in a Mathematical Dialogue	2022

Enfermería / Nursing

Article • *Open access*

1	Multiple Infections, Nutrient Deficiencies, and Inflammation as Determinants of Anemia and Iron Status during Pregnancy: The MINDI Cohort	2024
2	Factors associated with the consumption of fruits and vegetables in latin american university students Factores asociados al consumo de frutas y verduras en estudiantes universitarios de latinoamerica	2023
3	Barriers and Opportunities for Clinical Nutritionists in 13 Latin American Countries: A Qualitative Study	2023
4	Malnutrition and unhealthy eating habits in Panamanian firefighters Malnutrición e inadecuados hábitos de alimentación en bomberos de Panamá	2023

Profesiones de la Salud / Health Professions

Article • *Open access*

1	Assessment of the Quality, Chemometric and Pollen Diversity of <i>Apis mellifera</i> Honey from Different Seasonal Harvests	2023
2	Acute fetal cardiovascular adaptation to artificial placenta in sheep model	2023
3	Halo sign in fetal cytomegalovirus infection: cerebral imaging abnormalities and postmortem histopathology in 35 infected fetuses	2023
4	Brain cortical maturation assessed by magnetic resonance imaging in unaffected or mildly affected fetuses with cytomegalovirus infection	2023

Energía / Energy

Article • *Open access*

1	Contribution of Argentinian B Corporations to Sustainable Development Goals: Empirical Analysis Based on Their Practices and Solutions to Socioenvironmental Problems	2024
2	Spatial Analysis of Territorial Connectivity and Accessibility in the Province of Coclé in Panama	2023
3	A High-Voltage-Gain DC-DC Boost Converter with Zero-Ripple Input Current for Renewable Applications	2023

Ciencia de Materiales / Materials Science

Article • *Open access*

1	Characterization of the Stone Masonries and Evaluation of the Environmental Impact in Panamá Viejo: A Contribution for the Conservation of the Monumental Complex	2023
2	Comparison of Shear Bond Strength and Microleakage between Activa™ Bioactive Restorative™ and Bulk-Fill Composites—An In Vitro Study	2023
3	Binuclear Lanthanide Complexes Based on 4-Picoline-N-oxide: From Sensitized Luminescence to Single-Molecule Magnet Characteristics	2023

Decision Sciences / Decision Sciences

Article • *Open access*

1	Abundance, occurrence and time series: long-term monitoring of social insects in a tropical rainforest	2023
2	Assessing Panamanian hospitals' performance with alternative frontier methods	2023

Artes y Humanidades / Arts and Humanities

Article • *Open access*

1	Characterization of the Stone Masonries and Evaluation of the Environmental Impact in Panamá Viejo: A Contribution for the Conservation of the Monumental Complex	2023
---	---	------

Business, Management and Accounting / Negocios, Gestión y Contabilidad

Article • *Open access*

1	Assessing Panamanian hospitals' performance with alternative frontier methods	2023
---	---	------

Odontología / Dentistry

Article • *Open access*

1	Core Cariology Curriculum Framework in Spanish for Latin American dental schools: development and consensus	2023
---	---	------

Multidisciplinary / Multidisciplinar

Article • *Open access*

1	Social norms that sustain transactional sex and associations with sexual health outcomes: A mixed-methods study in the Comarca Ngäbe-Buglé, a rural-Indigenous region of Panama	2024
2	Climate change increases threat to plant diversity in tropical forests of Central America and southern Mexico	2024
3	Ongoing declines for the world's amphibians in the face of emerging threats	2023
4	Ecology of fear: Predator avoidance reduces seed dispersal in an ant	2023

La Universidad de Panamá amplía su Red Internacional de Investigación

Buscamos investigadores internacionales para el trabajo colaborativo en las siguientes áreas de conocimiento:

- Ciencias Agropecuarias y Biológicas
- Medicina
- Ciencias Ambientales
- Bioquímica, Genética y Biología Molecular
- Química
- Física
- Informática
- Ciencias de la Tierra
- Ciencias Sociales

Para más información escribenos a viceipup@up.ac.pa

The University of Panama is expanding its International Research Network

We are looking for international reserchers for collaborative work in the following areas of knowledge:

- Agricultural and Biological Sciences
- Medicine
- Environmental Sciences
- Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology
- Chemistry
- Physics
- Computer Science
- Earth Sciences
- Social Sciences

For more information write to us at viceipup@up.ac.pa

“Universidad de Panamá comprometidos con la Ciencia Abierta”

En una era donde la accesibilidad y la difusión del conocimiento son más críticas que nunca, el compromiso de la Universidad de Panamá con la promoción de la ciencia abierta se erige como un faro de progreso e innovación. Con más de 30 años de experiencia internacional en publicaciones académicas, he sido testigo del poder transformador de la investigación cuando se pone a disposición de un público más amplio. Este folleto es un testimonio del esfuerzo incansable de la institución para cerrar la brecha entre la investigación y la sociedad, incorporando los principios de transparencia, colaboración e inclusión que caracterizan el movimiento de ciencia abierta.

Las contribuciones presentadas en estas páginas no solo enriquecen el cuerpo de conocimiento existente, sino que también redefinen el panorama de la comunicación científica. Al priorizar el acceso abierto a los resultados de la investigación, esta institución empodera a los investigadores, profesionales y al público en general por igual. Los resultados presentados aquí reflejan una profunda comprensión de los desafíos que se enfrentan en los entornos de investigación contemporáneos, así como una dedicación inquebrantable para abordar estos desafíos a través de soluciones innovadoras.

Por otra parte, los conocimientos recogidos en este cuadernillo contribuyen significativamente al estado del arte de la comunicación científica, considerando como una visión a

los países de LATAM. Destacan las tendencias emergentes, las mejores prácticas y las consideraciones éticas que sustentan los paradigmas cambiantes del intercambio de conocimientos. A medida que navegamos por las complejidades de la era moderna de la información, las lecciones extraídas de estos estudios servirán como recursos invaluable para los académicos y las instituciones que se esfuerzan por mejorar su impacto y fomentar una cultura de apertura.

En conclusión, este folleto no solo es una recopilación de los resultados de la investigación, sino también un llamado a la acción para la comunidad científica mundial. Subraya la importancia de la colaboración y el intercambio de conocimientos como principios fundamentales que impulsarán los avances futuros. Felicito a la institución por su liderazgo visionario y su firme compromiso con la ciencia abierta, e invito a los lectores a participar en la investigación innovadora que se encuentra en estas páginas. Juntos, sigamos dando forma a un futuro en el que el conocimiento no conozca fronteras.

Dr. Francisco Farnum Castro
Coordinador de la Oficina de Publicaciones
Académicas y Científicas
Universidad de Panamá

“University of Panama committed to Open Science”

In an era where the accessibility and dissemination of knowledge are more critical than ever, Universidad de Panamá’s commitment to promoting open science stands as a beacon of progress and innovation. With over 30 years of international experience in scholarly publishing, I have witnessed the transformative power of research when it is made available to a broader audience. This booklet is a testament to the institution’s tireless effort to bridge the gap between research and society, embodying the principles of transparency, collaboration, and inclusivity that characterize the open science movement.

The contributions presented within these pages not only enrich the existing body of knowledge but also redefine the landscape of scientific communication. By prioritizing open access to research findings, this institution empowers researchers, practitioners, and the general public alike. The results showcased here reflect a deep understanding of the challenges faced in contemporary research environments, as well as an unwavering dedication to addressing these challenges through innovative solutions.

Moreover, the insights gathered in this booklet contribute significantly to the state of the art in scientific communication, considering as a view of LATAM countries. They highlight

emerging trends, best practices, and the ethical considerations that underpin the shifting paradigms of knowledge sharing. As we navigate the complexities of the modern information age, the lessons drawn from these studies will serve as invaluable resources for scholars and institutions striving to enhance their impact and foster a culture of openness.

In conclusion, this booklet stands not only as a compilation of research findings but also as a call to action for the global scientific community. It underscores the importance of collaboration and the sharing of knowledge as fundamental tenets that will drive future advancements. I commend the institution for its visionary leadership and steadfast commitment to open science, and I invite readers to engage with the groundbreaking research within these pages. Together, let us continue to shape a future where knowledge knows no boundaries.

Dr. Francisco Farnum Castro
Coordinator Academic and Scientific
Publications Office
University of Panama

Ponemos a disposición nuestras revistas científicas para la publicación de artículos

Contamos con revistas especializadas en temas relacionados con las Ciencias Físicas, Ciencias de la Salud, Ciencias Sociales y Ciencias de la Vida, así como varias revistas multidisciplinarias

Forme parte de nuestros equipos editoriales o de nuestros revisores
Escríbenos a publicaciones.cientificas.vip@up.ac.pa

Para más información sobre nuestras revistas científicas visite
<https://revistas.up.ac.pa>

We make our scientific journals available for the publication of articles

We have specialized journals on topics related to Physical Sciences, Health Sciences, Social Sciences and Life Sciences, as well as several multidisciplinary journals

Be part of our editorial teams or our reviewers
Write to us at publicaciones.cientificas.vip@up.ac.pa

For more information about our scientific journals visit
<https://revistas.up.ac.pa>

Nuestras Revistas Científicas 2024

Selección de Revistas en el Portal de Revistas de la Universidad de Panamá por área temática

- Artes y Humanidades
- Ciencias Agropecuarias
- Ciencias de la Ingeniería
- Ciencias Exactas y Naturales
- Ciencias Médicas
- Ciencias Sociales
- Multidisciplinar

Our Scientific Journals 2024

Selection of Journals in the Journal Portal of the University of Panama by thematic area

- Arts & Humanities
- Agricultural Sciences
- Engineering Sciences
- Exact & Natural Sciences
- Medical Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Multidisciplinary

Artes y Humanidades

Las Artes y las Humanidades abarcan una rica diversidad de campos que exploran las complejidades de la cultura, la sociedad y la historia humanas. Estas disciplinas van desde el estudio de las lenguas modernas hasta la exploración de las civilizaciones antiguas. Las materias clave incluyen artes, humanidades, lenguaje, poesía, música, obras clásicas, historia, estudios orientales, filosofía, arqueología, arquitectura, religión, televisión, teatro y radio.

Esta sección ofrece una amplia gama de contenidos, incluyendo artículos, cartas, editoriales, resúmenes de reuniones, erratas, poemas, cuentos, obras de teatro, partituras musicales, extractos de libros, cronologías, bibliografías y filmografías. Además, incluye citas de reseñas de libros, películas, música y representaciones teatrales, proporcionando un recurso completo para la investigación académica.

Arts & Humanities

The Arts and Humanities encompass a rich diversity of fields that explore the intricacies of human culture, society, and history. These disciplines range from the study of modern languages to the exploration of ancient civilizations. Key subjects include arts, humanities, language, poetry, music, classical works, history, oriental studies, philosophy, archaeology, architecture, religion, television, theater, and radio.

This section offers a wide array of content, including articles, letters, editorials, meeting abstracts, errata, poems, short stories, plays, music scores, excerpts from books, chronologies, bibliographies, and filmographies. Additionally, it includes citations to reviews of books, films, music, and theatrical performances, providing a comprehensive resource for scholarly research.

Cátedra

La revista Cátedra, especializada en estudios culturales y humanísticos, del Centro de Investigaciones de la Facultad de Humanidades de la Universidad de Panamá, publica material académico y científico, producto de la investigación (artículos, ensayos, entrevistas, reseña de libros), original e inédito.

Cátedra

The journal Cátedra, specialized in cultural and humanistic studies, of the Research Center of the Faculty of Humanities of the University of Panama, publishes academic and scientific material, product of research (articles, essays, interviews, book reviews), original and unpublished.

Cuadernos Nacionales

Es una publicación del IDEN (Instituto de Estudios Nacionales), ha querido salir de acuerdo a los nuevos parámetros exigidos para ser una revista indexada de la Universidad de Panamá. De acuerdo a estos parámetros, las revistas deben ser puestas en la web y así se facilita la lectura de sus contenidos a públicos académicos más diversos y más allá de las estrictas fronteras nacionales.

Cuadernos Nacionales

It is a publication of the IDEN (Institute of National Studies), it has come out according to the new parameters required to be an indexed journal of the University of Panama. According to these parameters, journals should be put on the web and thus facilitate the reading of their contents to more diverse academic audiences and beyond strict national borders.

REA: Revista Científica Especializada en Educación y Ambiente

La Revista Científica Especializada en Educación y Ambiente es una publicación especializada a cargo de la Extensión Universitaria de Soná. De carácter semestral, de acceso abierto y arbitrada, centra su atención en la promoción de la investigación en dos vertientes ineludibles y urgentes: las Ciencias de la Educación, las Ciencias Ambientales y Biología.

REA: Revista Científica Especializada en Educación y Ambiente

The Scientific Journal Specialized in Education and Environment is a specialized publication in charge of the University Extension of Soná. Of a biannual nature, open access and arbitrated, it focuses its attention on the promotion of research in two unavoidable and urgent aspects: Education Sciences and Environmental Sciences and Biology.

Revista Contacto

La Revista Contacto es una publicación académica de la Universidad de Panamá, en línea con acceso abierto y divulgación nacional e internacional en el área de Ciencias Sociales, Humanidades, Derecho y Ciencias Políticas. Es auspiciada por la Vicerrectoría de Investigación y Postgrado y se encuentra adscrita al Instituto de Derechos Humanos, Justicia y Paz. Recibe artículos inéditos en español o inglés indistintamente, siendo revisados en su lengua originaria, a través de un sistema de arbitraje

Revista Contacto

The journal is an academic publication of the University of Panama, online with open access and national and international dissemination in the area of Social Sciences, Humanities, Law and Political Science. It is sponsored by the Vice-Rector for Research and Postgraduate Studies and is attached to the Institute of Human Rights, Justice and Peace. It receives unpublished articles in Spanish or English indistinctly, being reviewed in its native language, through a double-blind peer review system.

Ciencias Agropecuarias

Las Ciencias Agropecuarias abarcan un amplio espectro de temas relacionados con la producción agropecuaria. Esto incluye la química y la biología, la genética y la mejora de plantas y animales. Otras áreas clave son climatología, maquinaria agrícola, economía, administración de empresas, botánica, fisiología vegetal, extensión rural, cereales y oleaginosas, fruticultura, silvicultura, entomología, hidrología, topografía.

Esta sección ofrece una cobertura en profundidad de estos temas, proporcionando información valiosa sobre las últimas investigaciones y desarrollos en ciencias agrícolas y disciplinas relacionadas.

Agricultural Sciences

Agricultural Sciences cover a broad spectrum of topics related to agricultural production. This includes chemistry and biology, genetics, and the improvement of plants and animals. Other key areas are climatology, agricultural machinery, economics, business administration, botany, plant physiology, rural extension, cereals and oilseeds, fruit growing, forestry, entomology, hydrology, topography.

This section offers in-depth coverage of these topics, providing valuable insights into the latest research and developments in agricultural sciences and related disciplines.

Revista investigaciones agropecuarias

La Revista Investigaciones Agropecuarias es un medio de divulgación científica de publicaciones especializadas en línea (ISSN L 2644-3856), arbitrada y seriada en el campo de las Ciencias Agropecuarias. Está bajo la responsabilidad de la Dirección de Investigación y Postgrado de la Facultad de Ciencias Agropecuarias de la Universidad de Panamá.

Revista investigaciones agropecuarias

The journal is a means of scientific dissemination of specialized online publications, refereed and serialized in the field of Agricultural Sciences. It is under the responsibility of the Research and Postgraduate Directorate of the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences of the University of Panama. Its online publication began in December 2018, with a biannual periodicity, corresponding to an annual volume, presenting a collection of original and unpublished scientific articles.

Revista Semilla del Este

La Revista Semilla del Este es una publicación científica y electrónica de la Universidad de Panamá, Especializada en Gestión Ambiental y afines, divulgada semestralmente, bajo la afiliación institucional: Universidad de Panamá. Centro Regional Universitario Panamá Este. Panamá.

Revista Semilla del Este

The Semilla del Este Journal is a scientific and electronic publication of the University of Panama, specialized in Environmental Management and related fields, published biannually, under the institutional affiliation: University of Panama. Regional University Center Panama East. Panama.

Ciencias de la Ingeniería

Las ciencias de la ingeniería abarcan una amplia gama de subcampos, abordando la naturaleza compleja e interdisciplinaria de la ingeniería moderna. Esta sección se centra en el modelado y la respuesta de materiales, junto con contribuciones que incluyen análisis teóricos, simulaciones numéricas y estudios experimentales en máquinas y herramientas.

Las áreas clave de interés incluyen la ciencia de los materiales, la dinámica y la fuerza de las máquinas, la mecánica computacional, las tecnologías energéticamente eficientes y la protección del medio ambiente. La sección también cubre los reglamentos técnicos, el apoyo metroológico y otros aspectos críticos de la ciencia de la ingeniería.

Engineering Sciences

Engineering Sciences encompass a wide range of subfields, addressing the complex and interdisciplinary nature of modern engineering. This section focuses on material modeling and response, alongside contributions that include theoretical analyses, numerical simulations, and experimental studies in machines and tools.

Key areas of interest include materials science, dynamics and strength of machines, computational mechanics, energy-efficient technologies, and environmental protection. The section also covers technical regulations, metrological support, and other critical aspects of engineering science.

REICIT

REICIT (Revista especializada de ingeniería y ciencias de la tierra). La Revista está orientada hacia la investigación científica de ingeniería y ciencias de la tierra, mediante un pensamiento crítico, constructivista y fenomenológico con todos sus componentes educativos, tales como: Ingeniería en Auditoría y Gestión de Procesos, Ingeniería en Prevención de Riesgos, Seguridad y Ambiente, Ingeniería en Operaciones Aeroportuarias, Ingeniería en Edificaciones, Ingeniería en Infraestructura.

REICIT

REICIT (Specialized Journal of Engineering and Earth Sciences). The Journal is oriented towards scientific research in engineering and earth sciences, through critical, constructivist and phenomenological thinking with all its educational components, such as: Engineering in Auditing and Process Management, Engineering in Risk Prevention, Safety and Environment, Engineering in Airport Operations, Building Engineering, Infrastructure Engineering, Industrial Engineering.

SusBCity

La revista SusBCity es una revista científica de publicación electrónica especializada en la sustentabilidad en el edificio y la ciudad. En la misma se publican artículos científicos originales desarrollados por profesores y estudiantes, trabajos de grado o tesis de licenciatura, resúmenes de tesis de maestría y resúmenes de proyectos de Doctorado.

SusBCity

SusBCity is a scientific journal of electronic publication specialized in sustainability in the building and the city. It publishes original scientific articles developed by professors and students, undergraduate or bachelor's theses, summaries of master's theses and summaries of doctoral projects. Most of the works are the result of the subject methodology of scientific and technological research and innovation of the Faculty of Architecture and Design, University of Panama (UP).

Enfoque

Enfoque es la revista científica de la Facultad de Enfermería de la Universidad de Panamá, tiene como objetivo compartir el conocimiento de la Enfermería con profesionales e investigadores en el área de la salud.

Enfoque

Enfoque is the scientific journal of the Faculty of Nursing, University of Panama, aims to share knowledge of Nursing with professionals and researchers in the area of health.

REA: Revista Científica Especializada en Educación y Ambiente

La Revista Científica Especializada en Educación y Ambiente es una publicación especializada a cargo de la Extensión Universitaria de Soná. De carácter semestral, de acceso abierto y arbitrada, centra su atención en la promoción de la investigación en dos vertientes ineludibles y urgentes: las Ciencias de la Educación, las Ciencias Ambientales y Biología.

REA: Revista Científica Especializada en Educación y Ambiente

The Scientific Journal Specialized in Education and Environment is a specialized publication in charge of the University Extension of Soná. Of a biannual nature, open access and arbitrated, it focuses its attention on the promotion of research in two unavoidable and urgent aspects: Education Sciences, Environmental Sciences and Biology.

Revista Colón Ciencias, Tecnología y Negocios

Revista Colón Ciencias, Tecnología y Negocios, la revista de divulgación de las Facultades de Ciencias Naturales, Exactas y Tecnología, Informática y Administración de Empresas y Contabilidad del Centro Regional Universitario de Colón, tiene como objetivo la difusión de nuevo conocimiento científico de alta calidad, producto del quehacer de docentes y estudiantes, con un alto sentido de responsabilidad en la procura constante hacia la excelencia académica.

Revista Colón Ciencias, Tecnología y Negocios

Revista Colón Ciencias, Tecnología y Negocios, the journal of dissemination of the Faculties of Natural and Exact Sciences and Technology, Computer Science and Business Administration and Accounting of the Regional University Center of Colón, aims to disseminate new scientific knowledge of high quality, product of the work of teachers and students, with a high sense of responsibility in the constant pursuit towards academic, scientific and research excellence, demanded by the university scientific community.

Scientia

Revista editada por la Vicerrectoría de Investigación y Postgrado de la Universidad de Panamá, cuyo fin es contribuir al avance del conocimiento de las Ciencias Naturales. Se publica en la modalidad de un volumen anual, que se divide en dos números o fascículos y ocasionalmente números especiales.

Scientia

Journal edited by the Vice-Rectorcy of Research and Postgraduate Studies of the University of Panama, whose purpose is to contribute to the advancement of knowledge of Natural Sciences. It is published in the form of an annual volume, which is divided into two issues or fascicles and occasionally special issues.

Tecnociencia

Bienvenidos a Tecnociencia, la Revista de divulgación científica de la Facultad de Ciencias Naturales, Exactas y Tecnología de la Universidad de Panamá, se publica semestralmente (enero-junio, julio-diciembre). Va dirigido a un público interesado en áreas específicas del conocimiento científico propias de la cobertura de la revista. La Revista Tecnociencia tiene como objetivo el estudio y la reflexión sobre teorías o conocimientos científicos, promover la investigación y evaluación de proyectos.

Tecnociencia

Tecnociencia, the scientific dissemination journal of the Faculty of Natural, Exact Sciences and Technology of the University of Panama, is published biannually. It is aimed at an audience interested in specific areas of scientific knowledge specific to the journal's coverage. The objective of the Tecnociencia Journal is to study and reflect on scientific theories or knowledge, to promote research and evaluation of projects, and to publish original and unpublished scientific and technical works.

Ciencias Médicas

La sección de Ciencias Médicas publica una amplia gama de artículos, incluidos trabajos de investigación, revisiones, editoriales, comunicaciones y más. Su objetivo principal es fomentar la publicación de resultados experimentales y teóricos con detalles completos, permitiendo la reproducción de experimentos y el avance de la ciencia médica.

Esta sección valora las contribuciones originales que hacen avanzar la ciencia o la práctica médica. Las publicaciones incluyen artículos, revisiones, seminarios, discusiones sobre políticas de salud, terapéuticas, cuadros clínicos, correspondencia e informes mundiales. La sección también presenta series y comisiones destinadas a impulsar cambios positivos en la práctica clínica y la política de salud global.

Medical Sciences

The Medical Sciences section publishes a diverse range of articles, including research papers, reviews, editorials, communications, and more. Its primary goal is to encourage the publication of experimental and theoretical results with comprehensive details, enabling the reproduction of experiments and the advancement of medical science.

This section values original contributions that advance medical science or practice. Publications include articles, reviews, seminars, health policy discussions, therapeutics, clinical pictures, correspondence, and world reports. The section also features series and commissions aimed at driving positive changes in clinical practice and global health policy.

Contacto Científico

La revista Contacto Científico, especializada en Odontología, es la revista oficial de la Facultad de Odontología de la Universidad de Panamá. Su objetivo es fomentar el espíritu de investigación entre estudiantes, profesores e investigadores del campo odontológico. Difundir información relevante y actualizada sobre la especialidad. Cooperar con la comunidad odontológica nacional e internacional con nueva información orientada a mejorar la atención al paciente, de acuerdo con los lineamientos dictados por las nuevas tendencias en el conocimiento.

Contacto Científico

The journal Contacto Científico, specialized in Dentistry, is the official journal of the Faculty of Dentistry of the University of Panama. Its objective is to promote the spirit of research among students, teachers and researchers in the dental field. To disseminate relevant and updated information on the specialty. Cooperate with the national and international dental community with new information aimed at improving patient care, in accordance with the guidelines dictated by new trends in knowledge.

Enfoque

Enfoque es la revista científica de la Facultad de Enfermería de la Universidad de Panamá, tiene como objetivo compartir el conocimiento de la Enfermería con profesionales e investigadores en el área de la salud.

Enfoque

Enfoque is the scientific journal of the Faculty of Nursing, University of Panama, aims to share knowledge of Nursing with professionals and researchers in the area of health.

REDEPSIC

REDEPSIC es una revista científica semestral especializada en la Facultad de Psicología de la Universidad de Panamá que publica contribuciones originales sobre avances y resultados de investigación. Se entiende por artículos científicos y técnicos los informes que describen los resultados originales derivados de proyectos de investigación básica o aplicada, investigación científica o desarrollo, generados por profesores, estudiantes o investigadores invitados.

REDEPSIC

REDEPSIC is a biannual scientific journal specialized in the Faculty of Psychology of the University of Panama that publishes original contributions on research advances and results. Scientific and technical papers are understood as reports that describe the original results derived from basic or applied research, scientific research or development projects, generated by professors, students or guest researchers.

Revista médico científica

La Revista Médica Científica es una organización estudiantil que desde su fundación ha tenido como objetivo promover el campo de la publicación en Panamá. En ella participan estudiantes de medicina y profesionales de diferentes áreas del ámbito biomédico.

Revista médico científica

The Scientific Medical Journal is a student organization that since its foundation has aimed to promote the field of publication in Panama. Medical students and professionals from different areas of the biomedical field participate in it.

Ciencias Sociales

La sección de Ciencias Sociales ofrece una plataforma para artículos de investigación, ensayos, notas didácticas y reseñas de libros sobre una amplia gama de temas de ciencias sociales y humanidades. También incluye informes sobre debates, acontecimientos, estudios de países, informes de conferencias, estudios de casos y exámenes.

Esta sección se compromete a fomentar diversas perspectivas y promover una comprensión integral en varias disciplinas. Al apoyar la experiencia académica y promover la comprensión multicultural y multirreligiosa, esta sección contribuye significativamente a la investigación mundial en ciencias sociales.

Social Sciences

The Social Sciences section offers a platform for research articles, essays, teaching notes, and book reviews across a wide range of topics in social sciences and humanities. It also includes reports on debates, developments, country studies, conference reports, case studies, and reviews.

This section is committed to fostering diverse perspectives and promoting a comprehensive understanding across various disciplines. By supporting scholarly expertise and advancing multicultural and multireligious understanding, this section contributes significantly to global social sciences research.

Acción y Reflexión Educativa

La revista Acción y Reflexión Educativa es una publicación especializada e indexada, del Instituto Centroamericano de Administración y Supervisión de la Educación (ICASE) de la Universidad de Panamá. Entre 1978 hasta el 2017, se publicó en formato impreso, y a partir del año 2018 está disponible en formato electrónico, con una periodicidad anual en el Portal de Revistas de la Universidad de Panamá. La Revista está orientada hacia la investigación, el debate y el pensamiento crítico sobre temas educativos.

Acción y Reflexión Educativa

The journal Acción y Reflexión Educativa is a specialized and indexed publication of the Central American Institute of Administration and Supervision of Education (ICASE) of the University of Panama. Between 1978 and 2017, it was published in printed format, and as of 2018 it is available in electronic format, with an annual periodicity on the Journal Portal of the University of Panama. The Journal is oriented towards research, debate and critical thinking on educational issues.

Analítica

Analítica es una revista especializada de filosofía, cuya dirección y edición está a cargo del Departamento de Filosofía de la Facultad de Humanidades, Universidad de Panamá. Su finalidad es fomentar la reflexión filosófica en Panamá y su objetivo es divulgar investigaciones y ensayos originales e inéditos en filosofía, realizados por autores nacionales e internacionales, escritos en español e inglés.

Analítica

Analítica is a specialized journal of philosophy, whose direction and edition is in charge of the Department of Philosophy of the Faculty of Humanities, University of Panama. Its purpose is to promote philosophical reflection in Panama and its objective is to disseminate original and unpublished research and essays in philosophy, carried out by national and international authors, written in Spanish and English.

Anuario de Derecho

El Anuario de Derecho es la Revista especializada y científica del Centro de Investigación Jurídica de la Facultad de Derecho y Ciencias Políticas de la Universidad de Panamá. Su objetivo es divulgar los avances y resultados de investigaciones originales e inéditas, así como documentos monográficos o de análisis o revisión; con contenido jurídico y político; realizados por autores panameños, preferentemente, e incluyendo participación de autores internacionales.

Anuario de Derecho

The Law Yearbook is the specialized and scientific journal of the Legal Research Center of the Faculty of Law and Political Science of the University of Panama. Its objective is to disseminate the advances and results of original and unpublished research, as well as monographic or analysis or review documents; with legal and political content; written by Panamanian authors, preferably, and including the participation of international authors.

Cátedra

La revista Cátedra, especializada en estudios culturales y humanísticos, del Centro de Investigaciones de la Facultad de Humanidades de la Universidad de Panamá, publica material académico y científico, producto de la investigación (artículos, ensayos, entrevistas, reseña de libros), original e inédito.

Cátedra

The journal Cátedra, specialized in cultural and humanistic studies, of the Research Center of the Faculty of Humanities of the University of Panama, publishes academic and scientific material, product of research (articles, essays, interviews, book reviews), original and unpublished.

Centros: Revista Científica Universitaria

Revista científica multidisciplinaria de carácter nacional e internacional que publica artículos originales de investigación, revisión y notas técnicas para divulgar resultados de trabajos de investigación pura, aplicada o formativa en las áreas de interés. Se publica semestralmente, de enero a junio, y de julio a diciembre. Presentamos una selección de artículos académicos destacados en las áreas de Ciencias Sociales y Ciencias Básicas.

Centros: Revista Científica Universitaria

Multidisciplinary scientific journal of national and international nature that publishes original research articles, reviews and technical notes to disseminate the results of pure, applied or formative research work in the areas of interest. It is published biannually, from January to June, and from July to December. We present a selection of outstanding academic articles in the areas of Social Sciences and Basic Sciences.

Cuadernos de Coyuntura

La revista Cuadernos de Coyuntura publica artículos y documentos producto de profundos análisis e investigaciones en los campos de la economía, finanzas y ciencias sociales. Los artículos que se presenten deben ser producto de un ejercicio de investigación original, apoyados en una realidad empírica significativa, o de reflexión teórica en ciencias económicas y sociales.

Cuadernos de Coyuntura

The journal Cuadernos de Coyuntura publishes articles and documents that are the product of in-depth analysis and research in the fields of economics, finance and social sciences. The articles presented must be the product of an original research exercise, supported by a significant empirical reality, or of theoretical reflection in economic and social sciences.

Cuadernos Nacionales

Es una publicación del IDEN (Instituto de Estudios Nacionales), ha querido salir de acuerdo a los nuevos parámetros exigidos para ser una revista indexada de la Universidad de Panamá. De acuerdo a estos parámetros, las revistas deben ser puestas en la web y así se facilita la lectura de sus contenidos a públicos académicos más diversos y más allá de las estrictas fronteras nacionales.

Cuadernos Nacionales

It is a publication of the IDEN (Institute of National Studies), it has come out according to the new parameters required to be an indexed journal of the University of Panama. According to these parameters, journals should be put on the web and thus facilitate the reading of their contents to more diverse academic audiences and beyond strict national borders.

CPA PANAMÁ

CPA Panamá es una revista de divulgación científica de la Facultad de Administración de Empresas y Contabilidad (FAECO) de la Universidad de Panamá, de periodicidad semestral. Su propósito es el abordaje de temas contables en todas sus ramas; auditoría, costos, administrativa, gubernamental, tributaria, sistemas de información, a través de investigaciones inéditas que constituyan un aporte para realzar la profesión, así como para la búsqueda de soluciones a problemas complejos que son de interés.

CPA PANAMÁ

CPA Panama is a scientific dissemination journal of the Faculty of Business Administration and Accounting (FAECO) of the University of Panama, of biannual periodicity. Its purpose is to address accounting issues in all its branches; auditing, costs, administrative, governmental, tax, information systems, through unpublished research that constitutes a contribution to enhance the profession, as well as for the search for solutions to complex problems.

D'Economía

D'Economía es una revista de carácter anual con ámbito internacional del Centro de Investigación de la Facultad de Economía (CIFE), que persigue un pensamiento diverso en el campo de la economía y las finanzas. Su principal objetivo es abordar los problemas socio-económicos y financieros mediante investigaciones inéditas basadas en el análisis científico y crítico de los problemas que aquejan a la sociedad nacional e internacional.

D'Economía

D'Economía is an annual journal with an international scope of the Research Center of the Faculty of Economics (CIFE), which pursues diverse thinking in the field of economics and finance. Its main objective is to address socio-economic and financial problems through unpublished research based on scientific and critical analysis of the problems that afflict national and international society, as well as to contribute to the advancement and development of knowledge through the contributions generated by published research.

Revista Colegiada de Ciencia

La Revista colegiada de ciencia del Centro Regional Universitario de Veraguas, Universidad de Panamá asume el reto estratégico de implementar acciones para garantizar impacto y visibilidad de la información científica en el país y en el ámbito internacional, manteniendo la calidad y el prestigio de la revista, mediante el cumplimiento de los criterios y normas establecidas. Este órgano de difusión de los trabajos científicos en una multiplicidad de campos.

Revista Colegiada de Ciencia

The Collegiate Journal of Science of the Regional University Center of Veraguas, University of Panama assumes the strategic challenge of implementing actions to guarantee impact and visibility of scientific information in the country and internationally, maintaining the quality and prestige of the journal, through compliance with the established criteria and standards. This organ disseminates scientific works in a multiplicity of fields of science.

Revista Colón Ciencias, Tecnología y Negocios

Revista Colón Ciencias, Tecnología y Negocios, la revista de divulgación de las Facultades de Ciencias Naturales, Exactas y Tecnología, Informática y Administración de Empresas y Contabilidad del Centro Regional Universitario de Colón, tiene como objetivo la difusión de nuevo conocimiento científico de alta calidad, producto del quehacer de docentes y estudiantes, con un alto sentido de responsabilidad en la procura constante hacia la excelencia académica, científica e investigativa que demanda.

Revista Colón Ciencias, Tecnología y Negocios

Revista Colón Ciencias, Tecnología y Negocios, the journal of dissemination of the Faculties of Natural and Exact Sciences and Technology, Computer Science and Business Administration and Accounting of the Regional University Center of Colón, aims to disseminate new scientific knowledge of high quality, product of the work of teachers and students, with a high sense of responsibility in the constant pursuit towards academic excellence. scientific and research demanded by the university scientific community.

Revista Contacto

La Revista Contacto es una publicación académica de la Universidad de Panamá, en línea con acceso abierto y divulgación nacional e internacional en el área de Ciencias Sociales, Humanidades, Derecho y Ciencias Políticas. Es auspiciada por la Vicerrectoría de Investigación y Postgrado y se encuentra adscrita al Instituto de Derechos Humanos, Justicia y Paz. Recibe artículos inéditos en español o inglés indistintamente, siendo revisados en su lengua originaria, a través de un sistema de arbitraje.

Revista Contacto

The journal is an academic publication of the University of Panama, online with open access and national and international dissemination in the area of Social Sciences, Humanities, Law and Political Science. It is sponsored by the Vice-Rector for Research and Postgraduate Studies and is attached to the Institute of Human Rights, Justice and Peace. It receives unpublished articles in Spanish or English indistinctly, being reviewed in its native language, through a double-blind peer review system.

Revista FAECO Sapiens

La Revista Contacto es una publicación académica de la Universidad de Panamá, en línea con acceso abierto y divulgación nacional e internacional en el área de Ciencias Sociales, Humanidades, Derecho y Ciencias Políticas. Es auspiciada por la Vicerrectoría de Investigación y Postgrado y se encuentra adscrita al Instituto de Derechos Humanos, Justicia y Paz. Recibe artículos inéditos en español o inglés indistintamente, siendo revisados en su lengua originaria, a través de un sistema de arbitraje

Revista FAECO Sapiens

The FAECO Sapiens Magazine is an online magazine published by the University of Panama-Faculty of Business and Accounting, biannually, with national and international circulation. It publishes unpublished manuscripts in Spanish and English that present research results or theoretical reviews that contribute to debates in the field of administrative sciences, specifically in the areas of administration and business.

Societas

La revista SOCIETAS es publicada por la Vicerrectoría de Investigación y Postgrado de la Universidad de Panamá desde 1999, con el fin de contribuir a la difusión del conocimiento de las Ciencias Sociales y las Humanidades. SOCIETAS es una revista científica especializada, indexada, de acceso abierto, con periodicidad semestral. Los artículos científicos que se someten a publicación son evaluados por especialistas en la materia siguiendo el método de "revisión ciega por pares".

Societas

The journal SOCIETAS has been published by the Vice-Rector for Research and Postgraduate Studies of the University of Panama since 1999, in order to contribute to the dissemination of knowledge of the Social Sciences and Humanities. SOCIETAS is a specialized, indexed, Open Access scientific journal, with biannual periodicity. Scientific articles that are submitted for publication are evaluated by specialists in the field following the "blind peer review" method.

Multidisciplinar

La sección de Ciencias Multidisciplinarias sirve como una plataforma dinámica para que académicos e investigadores de diversos orígenes académicos compartan hallazgos innovadores y fomenten la colaboración interdisciplinaria. Se dedica a publicar artículos de investigación de alta calidad revisados

por pares que abarcan múltiples disciplinas, incluidas la ciencia, la tecnología, la ingeniería, las matemáticas, las ciencias sociales, la educación y las humanidades.

Esta sección promueve un enfoque holístico para la resolución de problemas y la difusión de conocimientos, alentando a los investigadores a cerrar las brechas entre campos y explorar la interconexión de diferentes disciplinas. Al facilitar el intercambio de ideas, teorías y metodologías, esta sección hace avanzar tanto a la ciencia como a la sociedad.

Multidisciplinary

The Multidisciplinary Sciences section serves as a dynamic platform for scholars and researchers from various academic backgrounds to share innovative findings and foster interdisciplinary collaboration. It is dedicated to publishing high-quality, peer-reviewed research articles that span multiple disciplines, including science, technology, engineering, mathematics, social sciences, education, and humanities.

This section promotes a holistic approach to problem-solving and knowledge dissemination, encouraging researchers to bridge gaps between fields and explore the interconnectedness of different disciplines. By facilitating the exchange of ideas, theories, and methodologies, this section advances both science and society.

Revista Científica Guacamaya

La Revista Científica Guacamaya es una revista académica electrónica de corte multidisciplinario; con proyección nacional e internacional, a través de su página web publicará artículos originales, de revisión, notas cortas y ensayos. La Revista Guacamaya publicará semestralmente los resultados de connotados investigadores del Centro Regional Universitario de Coclé, de la Universidad de Panamá, así como también de otros investigadores de la Región, que desean compartir su trabajo inédito.

Revista Científica Guacamaya

Revista Científica Guacamaya is a multidisciplinary electronic academic journal; With national and international projection, through its website it will publish original articles, reviews, short notes and essays. The Guacamaya Journal will publish biannually the results of renowned researchers from the Regional University Center of Coclé, of the University of Panama, as well as other researchers from the Region, who wish to share their unpublished work.

Revista Científica Orbis Cognitionis

La Revista Orbis Cognitionis es un medio de divulgación de los aportes científicos de autores nacionales e internacionales al conocimiento, donde sus escritos son originales con contenido de actualidad y pertinencia social; del nuevo conocimiento suscitado de las actividades universitarias tanto de docentes como estudiantes del CRUSAM.

Revista Científica Orbis Cognitionis

The Orbis Cognitionis Journal is a means of disseminating the scientific contributions of national and international authors to knowledge, where their writings are original with current content and social relevance; of the new knowledge aroused from the university activities of both teachers and students of CRUSAM.

Revista Saberes APUDEP

La Revista Saberes APUDEP es una publicación científica bajo la responsabilidad de la Asociación de Profesores de la Universidad de Panamá, editada desde junio de 2018 en versión electrónica (ISSN L 2953-321X), con periodicidad fija semestral, de acceso abierto, arbitrada, que utiliza el sistema de evaluación externa por expertos, bajo la metodología de pares ciegos, conforme a las normas de la American Psychological Association (APA).

Revista Saberes APUDEP

Revista Saberes APUDEP is a scientific publication under the responsibility of the Association of Professors of the University of Panama, published since June 2018 in electronic version (ISSN L 2953-321X), with a fixed biannual periodicity, open access, refereed, which uses the system of external evaluation by experts, under the methodology of blind peers, in accordance with the standards of the American Psychological Association (APA).

Synergía

Synergía, surge como una propuesta innovadora del Centro Regional Universitario de Panamá Oeste (CRUPO), para la promoción del conocimiento científico y tecnológico, para gestionar un espacio que contribuya a la divulgación del conocimiento científico.

Synergía

Synergía, arises as an innovative proposal of the Regional University Center of West Panama (CRUPO), for the promotion of scientific and technological knowledge, to manage a space that contributes to the dissemination of scientific knowledge.

Visión Antataura

La revista Visión Antataura es una publicación de la Universidad de Panamá, bajo la dirección del Centro Regional Universitario de Azuero, presentada en formato digital con dos entregas al año. El contenido de la misma es multidisciplinario y se orienta al incremento de la participación de investigadores, profesores y estudiantes, nacionales e internacionales, en la generación y difusión del conocimiento, producto de estudios realizados, de innovaciones en distintas áreas del saber.

Visión Antataura

Visión Antataura is a publication of the University of Panama, under the direction of the Regional University Center of Azuero, presented in digital format with two installments per year. The content of the journal is multidisciplinary and is aimed at increasing the participation of researchers, national and international, in the generation and dissemination of knowledge, the product of studies carried out, of innovations in different areas of knowledge, as well as the critical analysis of historical, social, cultural and literary issues.

Universidad de Panamá
Publicaciones de
Investigaciones
y Revistas Científicas
2023 - 2024

Octubre 2024

University of Panama
Research Publications
& Scientific Journals
2023 - 2024

October 2024

